

TECHNOLOGICAL RECONDITIONING: A PILLAR OF CIRCULAR ECONOMY FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN FORTALEZA

The Case of Technological Reconditioning Centers in
Fortaleza as a Strategy for Sustainable Development
and Digital Inclusion

LUÍS FILGUEIRAS¹
luisedufill@gmail.com

SARAH PASSOS¹
sarahpassosbrasil93@gmail.com

SAMARA BRAGA¹
samarabraga367@gmail.com

CRISTINA ROMCY¹
cristinaromcy@unifor.br

¹University of Fortaleza

KEYWORDS

Sustainability, E-Waste, Reconditioning, Development, SDG

ABSTRACT

Electronic devices have become an integral part of daily life, connecting people and simplifying tasks. However, programmed obsolescence and excessive consumerism driven by technological innovation create a vicious cycle of consumption and disposal, worsening e-waste production and its environmental impact. To address this issue, CITINOVA established the Technological Reconditioning Centers (TRCs) in Fortaleza to combat e-waste and promote digital inclusion, aligning with the UN's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The TRCs collect, sort, and recondition discarded electronic devices, extending their life cycle and reducing environmental harm. These devices are redistributed to underserved communities, democratizing access to technology and offering training programs in computer assembly, maintenance, and repair, creating job opportunities for youth in disadvantaged areas. Ethically, the TRCs address both environmental responsibility and social equity, ensuring technology access for marginalized populations while reducing e-waste's environmental damage. Politically, the initiative highlights the importance of government policies that support sustainability and inclusion, in line with global commitments like the SDGs. The TRCs embody circular economy principles by extending device life, minimizing waste, and generating local employment. Based on documentary research and technical visits, the study shows the initiative's potential for replication in other cities, fostering a more sustainable future.

1. INTRODUCTION

In today's interconnected world, electronic devices play a pivotal role in daily life, streamlining processes and fostering global communication. However, this increasing reliance on technology has brought a sharp rise in e-waste generation, highlighting the environmental and societal challenges tied to our growing dependence on electronic products. The combination of constant technological innovations, the planned obsolescence imposed by the current market, and the appeal of more advanced devices leads to excessive consumerism. Fráguas and Gonzales (2020) highlight that this uncontrolled consumerism has altered people's consumption habits, resulting in a constant flow of waste generated by the replacement of devices, even when they are still functional.

All materials present in electronic devices can be recycled, but due to a lack of knowledge, coupled with insufficient information and poor awareness of proper disposal methods, 50 million tons of e-waste are generated annually worldwide, with only 20% properly recycled, according to the International Labour Organization (ILO) in a report from April 2019. When these devices end up in landfills or dumps, the chemicals used in their production (such as lead, mercury, and cadmium) can leak and contaminate the soil and water, affecting consumption chains and causing severe damage to ecosystems. Another possible fate for e-waste is incineration, which releases harmful air pollutants, including greenhouse gases (GHG). Beyond disposal issues, 80% of the carbon emissions associated with the lifecycle of electronic devices come from the extraction of minerals like lithium, platinum, and cobalt, used in the production of batteries and electronic parts. For instance, according to EcoDebate (2024), manufacturing a single smartphone emits approximately 85 kg of CO₂. This demonstrates how the lack of effective policies to control pollutants throughout the lifecycle of electronics significantly impacts human health and the environment.

In recent years, the dissemination of knowledge about the impacts of electronic waste and environmental awareness has led to a change in disposal practices. Governments, organizations, and the private sector have implemented policies to promote the collection, treatment, and proper reconditioning of such waste, aiming for a smaller carbon footprint. The circular economy, a production and consumption model that seeks to reduce the use of natural resources while reconciling economic growth with sustainability, has emerged as a sustainable solution to tackle the e-waste problem.

Recycling materials such as aluminum can save up to 95% of the energy

compared to producing from primary sources, avoiding significant emissions (O Eco, 2013). Additionally, by transforming waste into resources, the circular economy eliminates practices like incineration and improper disposal, which are major sources of greenhouse gas emissions. Recycling 1 million laptops, for example, can prevent the emission of 3,500 tons of CO₂, while reusing electronic components reduces the demand for mining, a carbon-intensive process (Green Elétron, 2021). Thus, the circular economy promotes a more efficient, sustainable system with a lower climate impact.

In this context, the United Nations (UN, 2015) established the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) within the 2030 Agenda for implementation by its member countries. SDG 13, or Climate Action, emphasizes carbon management as a crucial component for achieving this goal.

Fortaleza, the capital of the state of Ceará, the 4th largest city in Brazil, and the most densely populated, faces significant challenges in managing electronic waste, exacerbated by the high demand for technological devices and the planned obsolescence imposed by the market. This scenario led to the creation of the Technological Reconditioning Centers (TRCs), which stand out as an innovative solution to promote the circular economy by reconditioning electronic equipment and contributing to the reduction of waste and the carbon footprint in the city. Within this geopolitical and environmental discussion, the TRCs project is managed by the Foundation for Science, Technology, and Innovation of Fortaleza (CITINOVA), which is also responsible for other innovative projects aimed at the sustainable development of the metropolis.

Figure 1:
Electronics collection campaign organized by the TRC (Technological Reconditioning Center) of the University of Fortaleza (Unifor), aimed at promoting resource reuse and environmental awareness. Source: University of Fortaleza (Unifor).

This article explores how the TRCs in Fortaleza serve as an effective solution to the challenges of electronic waste, aligning with the

principles of the circular economy and the global decarbonization agenda. By investigating the environmental, social, and economic impact of these centers, we aim to demonstrate how they can serve as a replicable model for other cities seeking the transition to a more sustainable and inclusive future.

2. METHODOLOGY

The LivinLab research laboratory was created out of a concern for improvements in the city. The group contacted the Fortaleza Science, Technology and Innovation Foundation (CITINOVA). It was visit the CITINOVA whose aim is to stimulate creative energy, the dissemination of scientific knowledge and the development of technologies so that they result in solutions to urban problems and increase the well-being of the population. Taking Citinova's objective as a starting point, LivinLab was created to study and research the social programs that the Foundation has developed and their impact on the city of Fortaleza.

The research is aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), set by the United Nations to be met by countries by 2030. Among the 17 Goals, the one that best fits in with the research is SDG 12, which deals with responsible consumption and production. More specifically, it can be seen that Goal 12.5 is the one that best fits in with the objectives and study of the research, since it analyzes practices on how to reduce waste, especially electronic waste, through recycling and reuse.

The first step in the research to obtain the results was a pre-research moment with the data available on the Citinova website about the Fortaleza Technological Reconditioning Center (TRC). With the data collected, it was discovered that the program has five units in the following locations: Praia de Iracema, the first created; Bom-Jardim, inaugurated on November 30, 2023; Universidade de Fortaleza (UNIFOR), on April 10, 2024; Canindezinho, on July 18, 2024; and the Pici unit.

Figure 2: Classroom at the TRC (Technological Reconditioning Center) at the University of Fortaleza (Unifor), part of the initiatives during the 17th Environment Week. The space promotes digital education and the reconditioning of electronic devices. Source: Unifor News.

A case study/practice document was then drawn up, proposing an evaluation method based on questions from the environmental, social, economic and transversal dimensions, to be asked of those responsible for the TRC project, CITINOVA.

Based on the knowledge acquired, a visit was made to the headquarters of the CITINOVA foundation, in the Praia de Iracema neighborhood, and to the TRC at the University of Fortaleza to understand the implementation of the project. The visit sought to understand the purpose of the TRC, the destination of the technological material developed, the support provided by the city council, how registration and computer assembly training works, the difficulties already faced and how they have been overcome, as well as the current ones. As well as answering these questions, the visit allowed us to see the structure of the TRC. The combination of theoretical and practical data enabled an in-depth analysis of technological refurbishment as a factor in sustainable social and environmental development.

3. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The book *Cradle to Cradle: Remaking the Way We Make Things* by Michael Braungart and William McDonough (2008) establishes the connection between Technology Reconditioning Centers (TRCs) and the concept of a circular economy, proposing a cyclical system where everything can be reused or recycled. The authors emphasize waste as a design flaw and advocate the need to rethink the traditional production model to achieve greater sustainability. The circular economy offers significant benefits for a sustainable future by protecting the environment, reducing dependence on raw materials, and even generating employment opportunities.

The TRCs in Fortaleza have proven essential in promoting the circular economy by providing practical solutions to the city's growing problem of electronic waste. By refurbishing discarded electronics, these centers extend the life cycle of devices, reduce the environmental impact of waste disposal, and foster sustainability, contributing to lower carbon emissions. Furthermore, the program plays a critical role in digital inclusion by redistributing these devices to underserved communities, aligning with SDG 9 (UNICEF Brazil, 2024), which aims to ensure access to information and communication technology.

In collaboration with the Digital Youth Program, TRCs provide training in computer assembly, maintenance, and repair, empowering young people from low-income communities and improving their job opportunities. Since 2023, 173 students have completed training across 17 cohorts (Opinio CE, 2023). This initiative serves as a powerful tool to advance the 8th goal of the 2030 schedule, which focuses on promoting inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment, and decent work for all.

The first TRC in Fortaleza, inaugurated in November 2022, has already received 5 tons of electronic waste, of which 3 tons of unusable materials were sent to waste-pickers' associations for proper disposal, generating R\$20,000 in income, according to a 2023 report by Fortaleza City Hall. The report also highlights that recoverable materials, such as computers and laptops, are used in Digital Youth Program classes. Additionally, in September 2022, 15 waste-pickers' associations received refurbished computers to improve their operational workflows.

A remarkable innovation within the TRCs is the refurbishment of restricted devices, such as TV boxes, by removing illegal software and components, allowing their reuse for educational purposes and reintegrating them into a lawful usage cycle. Despite these advances, the program could benefit from greater visibility and support to expand its reach and impact. The image below depicts a TRC project that repurposes TV boxes for educational purposes.

Figure 3:
Educational Arcade generated at TRC UNIFOR, displayed at the Community Center of the University of Fortaleza. Source personal collection.

The TRCs initiative, in addition to aligning with SDGs 1, 8, and 9, also connects with SDG 12, which promotes responsible consumption and production patterns by encouraging sustainable practices in design, production, and disposal; SDG 13, which seeks effective actions against climate change by reducing improper electronic waste disposal and extending the lifespan of devices; and SDG 16, which contributes

to digital equity, strengthening the foundations for more just and inclusive societies.

Expanding the TRCs could bring socioeconomic benefits by distributing technological equipment that generates local employment, increasing the number of trained professionals, refurbishing more devices, and connecting education to employability, thereby contributing to a fairer and more inclusive society in line with SDGs 12 and 16. Public-private partnerships could enhance the program's sustainability, ensure funding, and integrate professionals into the job market, while technology companies could employ skilled workers and foster the circular economy.

However, challenges remain. The impact of the TRCs is limited by low public awareness and the modest scale of the program. While the initiative has established successful partnerships with educational institutions such as the University of Fortaleza and the Federal University of Ceará, broader outreach is needed to raise awareness about proper electronic waste disposal and the availability of refurbished devices (Green Eletron, 2024).

The circular economy emerges as a transformative agent in building cleaner and more sustainable cities by eliminating waste and improving citizens' quality of life. In TRCs, this approach is directly connected to decarbonization, as it extends the lifespan of materials whose production would otherwise contribute to carbon emissions.

By recovering and refurbishing equipment, TRCs prevent the extraction and processing of new materials, such as rare metals and plastics, which generate significant CO₂ emissions. In doing so, they promote resource reuse and waste reduction, helping to mitigate climate change and aligning with global sustainability and decarbonization goals. Furthermore, by reducing the environmental impact of electronic waste and fostering responsible consumption practices, TRCs strengthen the transition to a low-carbon economy, essential for a more sustainable future.

Additionally, TRCs represent an example of innovative design, integrating technology with sustainability and social inclusion policies. They demonstrate how a circular policy model can be practically and scalably applied in cities like Fortaleza, positively impacting waste management, workforce development, digital inclusion, and greenhouse gas reduction.

4. CONCLUSION

The implementation of Technological Reconditioning Centers (TRCs) in Fortaleza exemplifies how innovative design and ethical policies can converge to address pressing environmental and social challenges.

By aligning with principles of the circular economy, TRCs not only mitigate the harmful effects of e-waste on ecosystems and human

health but also reduce carbon emissions associated with the production and disposal of electronic devices.

From an ethical perspective, TRCs prioritize sustainability and inclusivity, offering vulnerable communities access to reconditioned technologies and fostering digital inclusion. This approach aligns with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly Goals 12 and 13, which emphasize responsible consumption and urgent climate action. Moreover, the TRCs' integration of waste-picker associations and youth training programs reflects a commitment to social equity and local economic development, illustrating how decarbonization policies can benefit society at large.

In terms of scalability, TRCs provide a replicable model for large cities worldwide. Their success lies in fostering collaboration between public institutions, private companies, and local communities, ensuring that the program addresses multiple dimensions of sustainability. To enhance their impact, policymakers must prioritize public awareness, strengthen partnerships, and secure funding to expand the reach of these centers.

Demonstrating how waste can be transformed into a resource and carbon-intensive processes minimized, TRCs present a forward-looking blueprint for cities striving to balance urban development with environmental stewardship. Their replicability underscores the potential for innovative policies to drive meaningful change in the fight against climate change and the pursuit of a circular, low-carbon economy.

By fostering responsible practices, social inclusion, and sustainability, initiatives like TRCs show us that it is possible to reimagine our impact on the planet and build a future where technology and the environment coexist in harmony, leaving behind a greener and fairer Earth for future generations.

REFERENCES

- Baron, D.P. (2008). *Cradle to Cradle: Remaking the Way We Make Things*. São Paulo: Gustavo Gili.
- Fraguas, T. & Gonzalez, C.E. (2020). 'Electronic waste in the context of environmental education: History and consequences', *Cocar: Cadernos de Comunicação e Artes*, 14(30), pp. 1-15.
- G1. (2024). 'Brazil ranks 5th in e-waste production, but correct disposal remains limited', G1, 27 April. Available at: <https://g1.globo.com/jornal-nacional/noticia/2024/04/27/brasil-e-o-5o-pais-que-mais-prod-uz-residuos-eletronicos-mas-descarte-correto-ainda-e-pequeno.ghtml> [Accessed 28 August 2024].
- Green Eletron. (2024). 'Which countries produce the most e-waste? See Brazil's position', Green Eletron, 15 March. Available at: <https://greeneletron.org.br/blog/quais-paises-produzem-mais-lixo-eletronico-no-mundo-vej-a-como-esta-o-brasil-neste-ranking/> [Accessed 28 August 2024].
- Elsevier. (2023). *Building a New System of Research Evaluation*. Available at: <https://www.elsevier.com/research-evaluation> [Accessed 28 August 2024].
- UNICEF Brazil. (2024). *Sustainable Development Goals*, UNICEF. Available at: <https://www.unicef.org/brazil/objetivos-de-desenvolvimento-sustentavel> [Accessed 28 August 2024].
- Green Eletron. (n.d.). 'Reciclagem de eletroeletrônicos e CO₂ na atmosfera', Green Eletron. Available at: <https://greeneletron.org.br/blog/reciclagem-de-eletroeletronicos-co2-na-atmosfera/> [Accessed 14 December 2024].
- O Eco. (n.d.). 'Reciclar pode ser a saída para fabricantes de alumínio', O Eco. Available at: <https://oeco.org.br/noticias/27149-reciclar-pode-ser-a-saida-para-fabricantes-de-aluminio/> [Accessed 14 December 2024].
- Green Eletron. (n.d.). 'Altas temperaturas no planeta: a importância da reciclagem', Green Eletron. Available at: <https://greeneletron.org.br/blog/altas-temperaturas-no-planeta-a-importancia-da-reciclagem/#:~:text=Lixo%20eletr%C3%B4nico%20e%20a%20emiss%C3%A3o%20de%20gases&text=Ruim%2C%20n%C3%A9%3F,de%20gases%20do> [Accessed 14 December 2024].

Mali Brasil Reversa. (n.d.). 'O impacto ambiental do lixo eletrônico: como ele afeta o planeta e o que podemos fazer sobre isso', Mali Brasil Reversa. Available at: <https://malibrasilreversa.com.br/blog/o-impacto-ambiental-do-lixo-eletronico-como-ele-afeta-o-planeta-e-o-que-podemos-fazer-sobre-isso> [Accessed 14 December 2024].

Meio Sustentável. (n.d.). 'Emissão de carbono', Meio Sustentável. Available at: <https://meiosustentavel.com.br/emissao-de-carbono/> [Accessed 14 December 2024].

Opinião CE. (n.d.). 'Resíduos eletrônicos: Prefeitura inaugura novo centro de recondicionamento tecnológico', Opinião CE. Available at: <https://www.opinioce.com.br/residuos-eletronicos-prefeitura-inaugura-novo-centro-de-re-condicionamento-tecnologico/> [Accessed 14 December 2024].